

MANIFESTATION OF THE CONNECTION BETWEEN MATHEMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN LESSONS

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Annotation: This article provides information on the use of information technology programs, electronic textbooks and virtual views in teaching mathematics.

Keywords: ICT, Movie Maker, electronic textbook, educational film, subject competence, virtual view.

INTRODUCTION

The main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic is the harmonious development and well-being of a person in all aspects, the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of personal interests, and the change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior. The formation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, on the basis of the achievements of modern culture, economy, science, technology and technology is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan [1].

MAIN PART

New information and communication technologies are currently one of the most relevant topics, due to the need to use different methods to study, research and gain experience in each field. Therefore, it is appropriate to use new information and communication technologies from the age of kindergarten until acquiring a perfect profession. Today's specialists, regardless of their sphere of activity, should have

extensive knowledge of informatics, modern computing techniques, information communication and communication systems, technical tools and their use, as well as the basics of new information technology and technology, its future, should incorporate knowledge about development. Due to the day-by-day development of modern computing techniques and information technology, and the increasing informatization of society, a number of educational subjects on informatics, computerization of production and management processes are included in the middle and upper stages of the continuous education system.

By the middle of the 20th century, fast machine mechanisms began to be used, complex techniques and technologies were invented. In the process of solving many issues, the volume of information has become an incalculable complex, and it is necessary to create means of collecting and transmitting this information, to determine the measures necessary for their timely processing and management. Improving management processes, introducing an information system, training specialists to work with a computer is important in the performance of many tasks, ICT tools can create the following opportunities for us [2]:

- ICT motivates students and increases their interest;
- ICT helps prepare students for their future careers. Nowadays, work activities are managed with the help of computers, technologies, programs and devices that students use with satisfaction;
- ICT opens up new opportunities for learning and teaching;
- ICT enables teachers to introduce new methods of teaching in their subjects, use new approaches, implement ideas and develop new skills for professional growth of teachers.
- ICT provides an opportunity for rational use of its resources;
- ICT saves time and money by intelligently managing and controlling the educational process. ICT shortens the preparation process for lessons and makes the learning process interesting and entertaining for students;

- ICT is flexible. ICT can be adapted for students of different ages, teachers at different levels, and supports both teachers and students in the educational process.

We know that the words of the Chinese philosopher Confucius 3500 years ago: "I forget what I hear, I remember what I see, I understand if I do it independently" are still being expressed today. When using informational and pedagogical technologies in education, students have the opportunity to hear, see and think independently based on what they see.

There are certain conditions for organizing classes using modern information technologies in the educational process. First, there must be information resources.

To these [3]

- personal computer;
- projector;
- multimedia tools;
- scanner (for transferring complex schemes and drawings, images on negative film to the computer);
- digital camera;
- video camera (for conducting video conferences and for other purposes);
- printer, copier (for copying and duplicating handouts, and more) and other resources.

The second is special software. In the educational system, multimedia are special programs needed to create electronic educational literature, lectures, virtual laboratory work, various animation programs, and more. There are many such programs, for example: Macromedia Flash MX is used to create animations. The well-known Power Point program is used to create multimedia presentations.

Description. The geometric locus of points whose sum of distances to two non-moving points in the plane is constant is called an ellipse. Let us be given two fixed points. These fixed two points are called focus. Let two points F_1 and F_2 be given in the plane. We draw a straight line through the points F_1 and F_2 and give

the direction to the straight line and call it the abscissa axis. We pass the ordinate axis through the middle of the points $F1$ and $F2$. We will show the students that we can draw an arbitrary ellipse on the plane using the GeoGebra Classic 5 program using the given data [4].

Photos developed in Photoshop or animations created with Flash can be easily placed in these presentations. In order to increase the interest of students in the teaching of mathematics, it is necessary to show them with the help of various programs.

CONCLUSION

In short, information and communication technologies create great opportunities for the professional development of teachers of mathematics. The main advantages of ICT are: effective management, storage and management of students' work by science teachers, as well as saving time. Saving time allows you to prepare well for training. Using ICT resources, science teachers not only update their knowledge, but also have the opportunity to gain theoretical knowledge.

REFERENCES

1. Kurbonov G.G. Advantages of computer educational technologies in teaching the subject of scalar product of vectors. *Journal of science and education*. 2020. No. 16(2. pp. 94). Part 33-36.
2. Boxodirova, F., Isroilova, D., Abduraxmanov, M., & Yuldasheva, D. (2022). DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING THE GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF CONJUNCTIONS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 1421-1422.
3. Xaitov, L. A. (2021, December). THE ISSUE OF SUSTENANCE AND PROFESSION IN HAKIM TERMIZI'S WORK "BAYANUL KASB"(“DESCRIPTION OF THE PROFESSION”). In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 67-69).
4. Хаитов, Л. А. (2014). Значение эстетического воспитания в развитии личности студента педагогического вуза. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (10), 40-44.
5. Azamatovich, X. L. (2021). The Concept of Heart In The Treatises Of Hakim Termizi. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 2(3), 63-67.
6. Ashurbayeva, R. Q. (2022). SHARQDA INTEGRATIV TA'LIMOTNING ILDIZI. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(08), 89-92.
7. Ashurbayeva, R. Q. (2022). INTEGRATIVE APPROACHES AND METHODS TOWARDS THE IMPLEMENTATION IN THE SYSTEM OF ADMINISTRATIVE EDUCATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 27, 60-65.
8. Yuldasheva, D., Ashurbayeva, R., Asadova, S., & Yusupova, D. (2019). Use of an Integrative Research on the Education System. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-4*, (November 2019), 7661.

9. Ашурбаева, Р. К. (2020). Интеграционный подход в системе образования. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 12 (64), pp. 61-63). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
10. Yuldasheva, D., & Ashurbayeva, R. Asadova Sh., Yusupova D. Use of an Integrative Research on the Education System. *Scopus: International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)* ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-4, November 2019.
11. Алиева, К. К., Ахмедова, Н. А., & Арипов, Ш. Ш. (2022). *Прогнозирование риска переломов у женщин фертильного возраста с ревматоидным артритом* (Doctoral dissertation, Санкт-Петербург).
12. Ахмедова, Н. А. (2022). The role of genes regulating inflammatory mediators in the etiopathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis.
13. Bozorova, D. B. (2015). SOME NOTES OF VARIABILITY IN THE UZBEK LINGUISTICS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 135-138.
14. Bazarova, D. (2022). VARIABILITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 483-486.
15. Bozorova, D. B. (2015). SOME NOTES OF VARIABILITY IN THE UZBEK LINGUISTICS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 135-138.
16. Алиева, К. К., Ахмедова, Н. А., & Ташпулатова, М. М. (2021). ИММУННЫЕ НАРУШЕНИЯ ПРИ СИСТЕМНОЙ СКЛЕРОДЕРМИИ. In *ДНИ РЕВМАТОЛОГИИ В САНКТ-ПЕТЕРБУРГЕ-2021* (pp. 10-10).
17. Ахмедова, Н. А., & Темирова, М. Б. (2022). *Влияние микробиоценоза кишечника на клиническое течение хронического панкреатита и его коррекция* (Doctoral dissertation, Ташкент).